

Hepatitis E virus in wild boars in Germany

BfR Information Nr. 012/2010, 1 March 2010

Hepatitis E is a virus-induced liver inflammation, which is relatively rare in Germany. Until now it has been assumed that human cases in Germany were mostly a result of travels to Asia and Africa where these diseases are more common.

Recent studies by the Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) and other research institutes indicate that on average 15% of wild boars hunted in Germany carry the hepatitis E virus. However, it is not clear so far, whether these viruses can be transmitted directly to humans.

For protection from infection with the hepatitis E virus, BfR recommends that consumers such as hunters should strictly keep sanitary conditions during carving up and that the meat should always be properly cooked before consumption. BfR has compiled a collection of consumer advice on kitchen hygiene.

The full version of this BfR Information is available in German on http://www.bfr.bund.de/cm/208/hepatitis_e_virus_in_deutschen_wildschweinen.pdf